

How is wind energy meteorology (mis)understood in past and recent studies on climate change's impact on future renewable energy?

Andrea N. Hahmann, Matti Koivisto, Marta Victoria
Aleksander Grochowicz, Lukas Alexander Karkossa
Master students: Jorge Soto Martin (2024) & Anna Sagués Mollà (2025)
PhD student: Graziela Luzia (2023)

DTU Wind and Energy Systems

VindKraftNet, Risø Campus, 15 April 2026

Motivation

- Harvesting electricity from renewable energy sources is vital in climate change mitigation.
- However, **climate change may influence the conditions in which wind turbines and PV panels operate** and the resources they are designed to harness.
- **Does climate research, so far, provide the data needed to answer these questions?**

Many options available now in all sectors are estimated to offer substantial potential to reduce net emissions by 2030. Relative potentials and costs will vary across countries and in the longer term compared to 2030.

What aspects of the simulated wind climate need to be accurately simulated?

The metrics needed to simulate the power system accurately depend on the application
 [Sorry. Models are imperfect! 😊]

Wind speed and direction distributions ➔ How much energy can a wind farm will produce?

Long-term averages and trends ➔ Would there be enough resources in the future?

Temporal correlations and auto-correlations ➔ How to design the power system to accommodate weather variability.

Spatial/temporal correlations ➔ Is there enough wind and solar energy to drive the energy system?

auto-correlation function

spatial correlation

correlation to measurements

Earth Mover's Distance

Luzia et al (2023)

Most modeling studies use

- Raw CMIP5/CMIP6/CORDEX data
 - wind speed at 10 m extrapolated to wind turbine hub height using a power law, with:
 - constant $\alpha = 1/7$
 - different $\alpha = 1/7$ for land; and $\alpha = 1/10$ for sea
 - α from a different model, e.g. ERA5
 - wind speed at GCM model height, interpolated to hub height
- Bias-corrected data using e.g. ERA5 data (ERA5 + Global Wind Atlas):
 - Bias correction using the ratio of the mean
 - Quantile-to-quantile, also called quantile mapping
- A combination of the above (most studies)
- Machine learning methods relating U at turbine height to 10-m wind and other atmospheric variables

For historical reasons...

In earlier studies (and new ones too), only 10-m winds were available, thus relying on empirical relationships to convert these to hub height

$$u(z) = \frac{u_*}{\kappa} \ln\left(\frac{z}{z_0}\right)$$

$$u(z) = u(z_r) \frac{\ln(z/z_0)}{\ln(z_r/z_0)}$$

$$u(z) = u(z_r) \left(\frac{z}{z_r}\right)^\alpha$$

constant

Assumptions:

Grounded on Monin-Obukhov similarity theory

Neutral atmospheric stability (no thermal stratification)

Horizontally homogeneous terrain

Valid typically in the **lowest ~50–100 m** of the atmosphere

Since surface roughness is not often available:

Over a limited height interval (e.g. 10–100 m), the logarithm varies slowly. We can linearize it in log–log space.

Power law, but the exponent should not be a constant

$$\alpha(z) = \frac{1}{\ln(z/z_0)}$$

for $z=100\text{m}$ and $z_0=0.1\text{ m}$ (grass)

$\alpha = 1/6.9$ or about $1/7$

$$U(z=100\text{m}) = 1.389 U(z=10\text{m})$$

Jorge Soto Martin, MS thesis 2024

CMIP6 100 m winds (1995-2014)

HadGEM3-GC31-MM

\bar{U} (z=100 m) from
 CMIP6 model level

What is the long-term mean wind speed
 (m/s) at 100 m using these assumptions?
 Mean 1995-2014. HadGEM3 model

PL (1995-2014)

HadGEM3-GC31-MM

\bar{U} (z=10 m) using power
 law and $\alpha=1/7$

PL-O (1995-2014)

HadGEM3-GC31-MM

\bar{U} (z=10 m) using power law and
 $\alpha=1/7$ (land), $\alpha=1/10$ (ocean)

PL-ERA5 (1995-2014)

HadGEM3-GC31-MM

\bar{U} (z=10 m) using power law and α
 from ERA5

Bias correction

$$U_{100,m-p} = U_{10,m-p} \left(\frac{\bar{U}_{100,ERA5}}{\bar{U}_{10,m-p}} \right)$$

$$U_{100,m-f} = U_{10,m-f} \left(\frac{\bar{U}_{100,ERA5}}{\bar{U}_{10,m-p}} \right)$$

Assumption:

Model error and shear are independent of time period

Not like using the ERA5 shear coefficient

HadGEM3-GC31-LL (50°N, 9°E) for Past Period

HadGEM3-GC31-LL (50°N, 9°E) for Future Period

Quantile mapping

(non-parametric Empirical Quantile Mapping)

The central assumption of quantile mapping is that the **relationship between simulated and observed distributions is stationary in time.**

Jorge Soto Martin, MS thesis 2024

HadGEM3-GC31-LL (50°N, 9°E) for Past Period

HadGEM3-GC31-LL (50°N, 9°E) for Future Period

ΔU : Annual

$$\Delta U = \bar{U}_f - \bar{U}_p = \bar{U}_{2051-2070} - \bar{U}_{1995-2014}$$

(a) CMIP6 raw 100-m

(b) CMIP6 10-m Power Law

(c) CMIP6 10-m PL Land/Ocean

 (d) CMIP6 10-m PL α ERA5

(e) CMIP6 Bias Corr

(f) CMIP6 QQ Corr

No dots:
 >75% of
 models (of
 a total of
 13) agree
 on the sign

Jorge Soto Martin, MS thesis 2024

Why Poland?

Jorge Soto Martin, MS thesis 2024 Land cover change 1995-2014 to 2051-2070

$$\Delta U = \bar{U}_f - \bar{U}_p = \bar{U}_{2051-2070} - \bar{U}_{1995-2014}$$

ΔU : Summer

Relocation
of the
Azores
High in the
future

Jorge Soto Martin, MS thesis 2024

Delta U (future – past)

For all models and grid points north of 36° North

Delta P (future – past)

For all models and grid points north of 36° North

Why use wind power density?

Jorge Soto Martin, MS thesis 2024

Comparative Analysis of Projections (Annually)

Jorge Soto Martin, MS thesis 2024

Spatial planning assumptions

But where should we put the wind turbines?

Common assumption:

All wind turbines at the centre of the grid experience the mean wind speed

Capacity density (CF) at the scale of a Climate Model grid size – From GWA <https://globalwindatlas.info/en/>

wind speed cumulative distribution for that area

Other approaches

- Present and future wind speed with known wind farm locations ($U_{ERA5/MIP/CORDEX}/U_{GWA}$)
- A few new studies use the spatial variability of wind speed to correct climate model values as aggregated values

Why do we need this?

ERA5 contains biases relative to observations in areas of complex topography

From NEWA paper, part 2
<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-13-5079-2020>

Energy production for the planned North Sea Energy Island

10 wind farms x 67 turbines x 15 MW reference wind turbine (NREL)

Jensen engineering **wake model**

Wind speed and direction from 16 CMIP6 models (AEP within 10% of the value calculated by using ERA5), wind time series at 150 m AMSL

Change in Energy Production for the Energy Island cluster
(2031-2050) minus (1995-2014)

Hahmann et al (2022)

Validation of Euro-CORDEX simulations against wind power generation

Table 1

Details of the EURO-CORDEX climate simulations. Heights are the number of heights above ground level: a combination of near-surface (10 m) with either one (100 m) or five (50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 m) fixed levels of wind speed, according to the ESGF availability for each model. For models with more than one available scenario, the bold RCP name indicates the representative model used in the validation.

Forcing GCM/ESM	RCM	Short name	Experiments	Heights	References
CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5 ^a	ALADIN63 ^b	CNRM_A	RCP2.6 , RCP8.5	6 levels	^a [41], ^b [42],
MOHC-HadGEM2-ES ^c	ALADIN63	MOHC_A	RCP8.5	6 levels	^c [43]
NCC-NorESM1-M ^d	ALADIN63	NCC_A	RCP8.5	6 levels	^d [44]
CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5	RegCM4-6 ^e	CNRM_R	RCP8.5	2 levels	^e [45]
ICHEC-EC-EARTH ^f	RegCM4-6	ICHEC_R	RCP8.5	2 levels	^f [46]
MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR ^g	RegCM4-6	MPI_R	RCP2.6 , RCP8.5	2 levels	^g [47]
NCC-NorESM1-M	RegCM4-6	NCC_R	RCP2.6 , RCP8.5	2 levels	

Fig. 2. Location of wind power plants operating in 2018.

Luzia et al (2023)

Capacity factor =
Energy
Produced/Energy
produced at full
operation

The capacity factor (CF) error is computed as the difference between the measured and simulated CFs for all 12 European countries, using the ERA5 and EURO-CORDEX models. GWA2 scales the top 7 models (names starting with “g”). The last two columns show the mean and the standard deviation for all countries.

Luzia et al (2023) - <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.118989>

The future of energy production in Europe according to CORDEX

Raw versus bias-corrected (using Global Wind Atlas wind speeds); 2006-2025 compared to 2046-2065

Luzia et al (2023) - <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.118989>

Processing of CMIP6 data using ERA5 and GWA

Data processing workflow
 CMIP6 100 and 200 m winds
 BC using ERA5+GWA, with
 separate corrections for land
 and sea
 Conversion to power

Anna Sargues MS thesis (2025)

Figure 4.3: Power Curve for the Chosen Turbines (onshore and offshore)

Bias factors per model

High Resolution
0.8°

Low Resolution
2.8°

Figure 5.1: Distribution of the bias factors for each model (colored by Model Type, sorted by decreasing grid resolution)

Anna Sargues MS thesis (2025)

Relative change in CF per season EoC (2035-2070) - BoC(1980-2015)

Figure 5.4: Seasonal agreement plots for relative change in capacity factor. Areas where fewer than 75% (11/14) of models agree on the sign of change are masked.

Anna Sargues MS thesis (2025)

Final thoughts...

- Extrapolating wind speeds from 10 meters to turbine height using a constant-exponent power law is a poor approximation and often exaggerates future changes in wind resources. Some bias correction methods ameliorate these issues, but do not totally resolve them
- The full chain of models is necessary to understand the effects of climate change on future power generation. Simple approximations are often misleading.
- Wind speeds from CORDEX represent power generation in Europe very well when bias-corrected using the GWA (as in other studies).
- As more complex statistics are examined (e.g., wind power droughts and Time of Emergence), the importance of post-processing assumptions increases.

References

- N. N. Davis, et al. “The Global Wind Atlas: A High-Resolution Dataset of Climatologies and Associated Web-Based Application”. *Bull of the American Meteorological Society* 104 (2023): 1507–1525.
- G. Luzia, M. J. Koivisto, A. N. Hahmann. “Validating EURO-CORDEX climate simulations for modelling European wind power generation”. *Renewable Energy* 217 (2023): 118989.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960148123008959>.
- A. N. Hahmann, O. Garcia-Santiago, A. Peña. “Current and future wind energy resources in the North Sea according to CMIP6”. *Wind Energy Science* 7, no. 6 (2022): 2373–2391. <https://wes.copernicus.org/articles/7/2373/2022/>.
- G. Luzia, A. N. Hahmann, M. J. Koivisto. “Evaluating the mesoscale spatio-temporal variability in simulated wind speed time series over northern Europe”. *Wind Energy Science* 7, no. 6 (2022): 2255–2270.
<https://wes.copernicus.org/articles/7/2255/2022/>.
- M. Dörenkämper, et al. “The Making of the New European Wind Atlas – Part 2: Production and evaluation”. *Geoscientific Model Development* 13, no. 10 (2020): 5079–5102.
<https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/13/5079/2020/>.
- A. N. Hahmann, et al. “The making of the New European Wind Atlas – Part 1: Model sensitivity”. *Geoscientific Model Development* 13, no. 10 (2020): 5053–5078. <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/13/5053/2020/>.

DTU

